

SMART COMPOSITE LAMINATES INCORPORATING STRAIN MEMORY ALLOY FOILS

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SUMMARY: The escalating usage of composite laminates in safety critical structures requires accurate damage assessment techniques. A robust technology based on the incorporation of strain memory foils within the laminate, has been developed. These strain memory foils transform from a metastable austenitic parent phase (at room temperature range) which is paramagnetic to a ferromagnetic martensitic product phase, in direct proportion to the peak strain induced in the material. The resulting change in magnetic susceptibility can be measured and correlated back to the peak strain experienced by the material (strain memory effect). This paper presents the test results that show that it is possible to manufacture a smart laminate with embedded strain memory foils, and indeed induce sufficient strain in the foils to provide a significant and measurable change in magnetic susceptibility. Various foil geometries and laminate thicknesses are also tested for their effect on the susceptibility measurements.

KEYWORDS: strain memory, intelligent laminate, structural health monitoring.

INTRODUCTION

The increasing frequency with which composite laminates are used in safety critical applications requires the use of reliable methods of damage assessment and structural health interrogation. The nature of composite laminates poses challenges in this regard, and many researchers have investigated the use of piezoelectric patches, fiber optics, and even the intrinsic piezoresistive properties of carbon fibers themselves, as a means of producing reliable structural health monitoring data. The above-mentioned methods, have all achieved a measure of success, some at greater cost than others, but there is still space in the market for a robust system (capable of easily withstanding curing temperatures and regimes) that is cost effective and simple to interrogate.

A class of smart materials known as strain memory alloys shows great potential for the production of a structural health monitoring system that can be remotely interrogated if necessary. Strain memory alloys are austenitic at room temperature, but are metastable with respect to deformation. Once strained, the metastable austenite (FCC) begins to transform to thermodynamically stable (BCC or BCT) martensite, which is ferromagnetic compared to the paramagnetism displayed by the parent austenite. The transformation is irreversible, and therefore only successively higher levels of strain are “recorded” within the material’s microstructure. This phenomenon makes strain memory alloys useful as **passive peak strain sensors** that are capable not only of sensing, but also of bearing significant load, effectively allowing a dual-use component or smart component.

The strain memory alloy is added to the laminate at the primary production phase, and (at this point) takes the form of a thin plate (foil). Provided that there is adequate bonding between the laminate and the smart insert, the load will be transferred to the strain memory alloy as the laminate is strained, and a measurement of the changing magnetic signature of the strain memory alloy can then be correlated with the accumulated damage of the laminate. This changing magnetic susceptibility must be measured by a non-contact sensor (because the strain memory insert is embedded within the laminate) that generates a trigger if the level of damage detected exceeds a pre-defined value, which then uses modem technology to send a short text message to a pre-determined cell-phone or SIM card, warning the responsible engineer of the need for maintenance and/or repair. The system is illustrated in the flow diagram shown in figure 1 below.

Fig. 1: The smart laminate system

1. STRAIN MEMORY ALLOYS

Strain memory alloys have found application in a variety of smart components that have been developed to the point of commercial prototypes, such as a smart aircraft bolt, a smart rock anchor for mines, a smart r-bar for civil applications, and smart washers for general use. In all of the above applications, the strain memory alloy performs a significant load-bearing activity as part of a dual use component. For example, the smart aircraft bolt looks exactly like the normal bolt, but is entirely constructed from an ultra-high strength strain memory alloy that when interrogated will indicate whether there is any crack initiation site present in the bolt.

To embed a strain memory alloy insert into a composite laminate is however slightly different in a number of respects:

- 1) The strength levels required are quite low, in fact the metal insert should not bear significant loading, because there would then be a risk of the insert pulling out of the laminate, instead of indicating potential problems within the laminate. Thus the strain memory alloy acts primarily in a damage indicating capacity for this application.
- 2) The metal insert should be as small as possible, and as thin as possible, to provide the minimum disturbance (or negative stress concentration effect) on the laminate. Satisfying this requirement means that the volume of martensite actually forming (across such a thin cross-section) is extremely small. Detecting this small volume poses challenges for magnetic susceptibility measurement equipment.
- 3) In all of the other applications of strain memory alloys, mentioned above, the most effective manner in which to monitor the changing magnetic susceptibility, was to use an inductance coil wound around the strain memory alloy. By passing a current through the coil, the changing inductance (caused by the changing magnetic

susceptibility of the strain memory core) could be read quite simply. It is not however feasible to embed a coil wound around the strain memory insert, within a composite laminate. The sensor capturing the magnetic susceptibility therefore has to be a non-contact sensor capable of detecting minute amounts of martensite. A custom sensor was therefore built.

The key to producing an alloy, which will transform upon application of stress or strain, is to carefully engineer the degree of austenitic stability. [1, 2, 3, 4, 5] In order to accomplish this, two factors need to be taken into account: the alloying chemistry, and the amount of Prior Deformation of Austenite (PDA). [6,7] A careful consideration of these two factors will produce a strain memory alloy that is matched in terms of strength and transformation characteristics (when and how fast the alloy transforms to martensite) to the particular application, while still having the other required properties such as corrosion resistance, fatigue strength, etc.

1.1 Alloying Chemistry

The metastability which essentially imparts the strain memory to an alloy, does not belong to a confined group of ferrous alloys; the formulation may be as simple as Fe-Ni, or as complex as Fe-Ni-Cr-Mo-Si-C-Mn, the most fundamental consideration being what effect each alloying element has on the austenitic stability of the final alloy. Elements such as Chromium, which have a BCC structure, obviously tend to stabilize the BCC martensite phase, while elements such as Nitrogen, Nickel, and Manganese stabilize the austenitic structure (FCC).

1.2 Prior Deformation of Austenite

Prior Deformation of Austenite (PDA) refers to the warm work that is put into the material at temperatures between 450⁰C and 550⁰C. It usually takes the form of warm rolling. The effect of PDA is not only to increase the strength of the material (without transforming it to martensite as would happen at room temperature) but also to destabilise the austenite with respect to deformation at room temperature, i.e. the greater the percentage of PDA the easier the austenite will transform to martensite.

2. SMART LAMINATES

For the purpose of proving the strain memory concept applicable to composite laminates, strips of strain memory alloy were inserted into the centre of laminates for tensile testing. The strain memory alloy used was an Fe-Cr-Ni alloy, with a proven transformation record. Although rolled to **very** thin plate, the level of **warm** work put into the material was nil, as the strengths of the laminate and the smart insert had to be matched. The smart inserts were machined using Electro-Discharge Machining (EDM) because conventional machining would have caused a premature martensitic transformation.

2.1 Experimental Procedure

A vacuum bagging process was used to produce the test pieces: mould surfaces were coated with release agent, half of the total number of layers of fibre were placed in the mould, then a strain memory alloy strip was inserted. The remaining half of the fibre layers was then laid up in a similar manner. The lay-up was covered with a perforated release material followed by the breather material. The vacuum bag was then sealed and a vacuum of -85 KPa to -90KPa

applied. The lay-up was allowed to stand for at least 24 hours before the vacuum bag was removed and samples allowed to cure. The laminate was manufactured using unidirectional glass fibres (190g) with epoxy resin (trade designation LH22 with hardener LH281). The number of layers of glass was varied (10 and 16) in order to determine the effect of the thickness of the laminate on the sensitivity of the magnetic susceptibility reading obtained from the smart insert. A variety of smart insert geometries were tested as can be seen in figure 1 below. All of the strips were 220 mm long, and 3 mm wide. A section 20mm long at each end was made slightly wider for ease of lay-up. The first shape is a straight strip that is not narrowed at the region of magnetic susceptibility measurement i.e. straight. The remaining geometries of the smart strips are narrowed at the centre, in the region of magnetic susceptibility measurement. The length of this narrowed section varied: 5mm (figure 2(b)) and 10mm (figure 2(c)). The width of the narrow section was fixed at 2 mm. The laminates were cut into tensile test shape using water jet cutting, and an example of the finished product can be seen in figure 3 below.

Fig. 2: Smart Insert Geometries: (a) Straight Insert, (b) 5mm long Narrowed-Section Insert, (c) 10mm long Narrowed-Section Insert.

Fig. 3: A schematic of the Tensile Laminate Specimen with Smart Insert.

The tensile testing was performed on an Instron tensile test rig, at a strain rate of 2 mm/mm/min. The changing magnetic susceptibility of the strain memory alloy inserts was measured using a non-contact GMS-2 susceptibility sensor. This sensor is a commercially available sensor with a circular probe approximately 30mm in diameter. The probe was fixed very carefully in a mounted position on the frame of the Instron testing machine. Readings of magnetic susceptibility were taken at displacement increments of 0.5mm.

2.2 Results

The tensile load and magnetic susceptibility are both plotted against the extension of the laminate, and several test pieces of each type were manufactured and tested to failure. The graphical results are presented below in figures 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9.

Fig. 4: Tensile Test of Straight Insert Smart Laminates: Load vs Extension

Fig.5: Tensile Test of 5mm Narrowed Section Insert Smart Laminates: Load vs Extension.

Fig. 6: Tensile Test of 10mm Narrowed Section Insert Smart Laminates: Load vs Extension

Fig. 7: Tensile Test of Straight Insert Smart Laminate (10 layers): Susceptibility vs Extension.

Fig. 8: Tensile Test of Narrowed Section Insert Smart Laminate (10 layers): Susceptibility vs Extension

Fig. 9: Tensile Test of Narrowed Section Insert Smart Laminate (16 layers): Susceptibility vs Extension

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The testing produced repeatable results in terms of the loading, as well as susceptibility ranges that were reached. There were no problems with delamination or bonding between the smart inserts and the laminate. Figure 4, 5 and 6 show that the ranges of failure load were constant

(between 12000 and 17000N) whether the smart insert was straight or contained a narrowed section of 5mm or 10mm (see figure 2 (b) and (c)). The extensions were on average between 5 and 6mm for each type of smart insert (see figure 2). Thus the presence of the narrowed section had no effect on the strength or ductility of the smart laminate. This is to be expected, since the insert was designed specifically in terms of strength, transformation characteristics and dimensions, to alter the laminate characteristics as little as possible.

Figures 7, 8, and 9, however, show clearly that the presence of a narrowed section or damage concentrator influences the magnetic susceptibility readings. A straight insert (figure 2(a)) produces a maximum magnetic susceptibility of 350, while an insert with a narrowed section produces a maximum susceptibility of 700. In effect the production of martensite is concentrated in the narrower region of the insert, resulting in greater susceptibility measurements. Not unexpectedly, the laminates with 16 layers (instead of 10) showed a reduction in magnetic susceptibility measured, with a maximum of 500. The distance of the smart insert (and hence the martensite) from the meter has a significant effect on the sensitivity of the susceptibility reading.

The particular magnetic susceptibility meter used to conduct the tests would not be suitable for practical applications of this technology, and another more sensitive (in terms of the amounts of martensite that can be detected) and robust sensor has been developed to fit with the modern technology that sends a message to a cell-phone if a pre-defined level of damage has been exceeded.

The fact that the readings were consistent within the test piece types and displayed an almost linear relationship to the extension of the test piece suggests that the technology is effective. And, further development is planned for specific applications, such as wind turbine blades.

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